

The Funneling Effect: A prototype implementation of an illusory sense of touch in virtual reality

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Figure 1: The Vibrotactile Funneling Illusion to create an “out-of-the-body” touch Illusion: The First person perspective of the hands as seen through the head-mounted display during the conditions when a virtual ruler was rendered between the virtual hands

ABSTRACT

This paper implements the “funneling illusion” in immersive virtual reality. The aim is to create a richer user experience by incorporating multiple senses, as well as, improving the sense of presence and sense of body ownership. In the future, we will experimentally test the hypothesis that vibrotactile stimuli delivered by two separate handheld VR controllers can elicit an “out-of-the-body” illusory sense of touch in virtual reality.

Index Terms: Human-centered computing—Virtual Reality—Illusory techniques—Multisensory Experiences; Sense of Presence—Body Ownership Illusion—Avatars

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1 INTRODUCTION

Virtual reality (VR) refers to a simulated environment that immerses the user into a computer-generated world, that might be related to or be totally different from reality [18]. Immersive VR allows for a stronger sensory immersion, and thus it is commonly used to stimulate various sensory modalities under different environmental conditions, often from an embodied first-person perspective [34]. Increasing the number of senses (e.g., taste, smell, touch, hearing, and sight) stimulated in VR can create the illusion of being present in that Virtual Environment (VE) and having the ability to act within this space - a feeling often referred to as “presence” [42]. Visual and auditory cues predominate in VR simulations, with less frequent use of other sensory cues such as haptic and vibrotactile feedback [9, 16].

New and innovative human-computer interaction (HCI) technologies are becoming increasingly popular due to the growing capabilities of interacting computing devices, such as VR systems. HCI dictates that an easy-to-use input device is employed, together with an output device that returns appropriate feedback to the user [35]. The study of input devices and technologies that provide interaction with greater immersion is an area of particular interest to the research community, and this includes the research on haptic interaction and feedback [28]. Gibbs, Gillies, and Pan (2022) [16] explored haptic and visual feedback of the participants’ sense of presence in VR. Results showed that haptic feedback contributes more to a sense

of presence in a VE than visual feedback alone. Participants were able to discern the location of phantom sensations more easily (for example, where a virtual ball bounced on a virtual ruler) when they receive haptic feedback as opposed to visual feedback.

This work focuses on VR experiments where the user experiences a sense of embodiment. That is, the user sees the virtual avatar as a representation of its own body from a first-person perspective [20, 26]. Roughly speaking, this means that the avatar is located in the same space as the user's body and is seen from the user's point of view. The user has control over the avatar's movement, and as a result, perceives the virtual body as their own. The more realistic an avatar's appearance is, the more realistic and immersive the experience will be. The sense of embodiment in VR, as described by Kilteni *et al.* [26], refers to the feeling of inhabiting and controlling a virtual body and is often connected to the following: the sense of self-location (or where you are), the sense of agency (or being able to move), and the sense of ownership (or feeling like the virtual body is yours). As a result, the sense of embodiment in VR may influence the user's perception of reality to the extent where the user identifies the virtual avatar as the source of their sensations [18, 43, 46].

The illusion of body ownership can be created by embodying an avatar under a variety of conditions [27, 33]. It is generally believed that the Body Ownership Illusion (BOI) is the result of the integration of sensory information (i.e., visual, tactile, proprioceptive, and sensorimotor). Research in this area shows that BOIs can have profound effects on how we interact with and perceive our environment [1, 17, 41], including our sense of touch in VR [25, 32].

The "tactile funneling illusion" is a major illusory feedback technique that occurs when two locations on the skin are stimulated simultaneously, leading to the illusory perception that the source of touch is coming from the space between the two points [49]. In this tactile illusion, two sources of vibrotactile stimuli of the same waveform and frequency are used. Then, varying the amplitude of the two sources, affects the perceived location of the vibrotactile stimuli. As a result of the nervous system's funneling action, phantom sensations can be felt between two disparate points [49]. This illusion demonstrates that our perception of touch does not always correspond to the site of physical contact with the skin [8].

In this paper, we use the tactile funneling illusion in an immersive VR setup to explore whether one's sense of touch could be extended to virtual objects that may or may not be visualised in the VE, when receiving visuotactile and auditory stimuli from a first-person perspective while one's eyes are open. Our prototype has the potential to give the sensation of touching a virtual object rendered between the avatar's hand. However, the user is required to hold an external object - a VR controller - which interacts with the VE, causing the user to have an "out-of-the-body" experience. This illusion of touch is robust when the vibrotactile stimuli follow the correct temporal pattern and are accompanied by corresponding visual stimuli at the illusory location [5, 6, 16, 17].

2 BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Our research builds on several related work areas, particularly tactile illusions, avatar embodiment, intersensory integration, and uncanny valley which will be reviewed in the following subsections.

2.1 Tactile Illusions

According to [5], our sense of touch is not just limited to the surface of our skin but can also be extended to virtual objects we are holding when we experience certain tactile illusions in VR settings where there are limited points of contact with the user. Thus, the way we perceive touch does not always match up with the location of where we are physically touched.

Berger *et al.*'s study [5] found that vibrotactile stimuli delivered by two separate handheld controllers can elicit an "out-of-the-body" illusory sense of touch in VR. The authors concluded that one's sense

of touch may be able to extend beyond the body and even into the void that surrounds us under certain conditions. These findings have implications for our comprehension of the human representation of touch and may offer a means to extend the sense of touch beyond the hands in VR systems by using two independent controllers. The work presented in this paper provides insights into how we perceive the sense of touch and how we can augment it using multimodal devices, wearable devices, and VR systems. Subsequent work by Gibbs *et al.* [16] found that an illusory "out-of-the-body" sense of touch can be elicited in an immersive VR setting using the tactile funneling illusion technique.

There has been a debate among psychologists and neuro-scientists about how the brain represents the sense of touch (illusory or otherwise), with some arguing that it is the product of activation of location-specific receptive fields in the primary somatosensory cortex [13, 15, 31], while others maintain that this does not adequately explain the influence of cognitive factors, such as selective attention, on our perception of touch [12]. Thanks to neuro-imaging technological advances, it is now well known that the illusory sense of touch is correlated with activation at the site of the primary somatosensory cortex that represents the portion of the skin where the illusory perception of touch was felt [7]. This confirms that our sense of touch, even when illusory, is represented by the primary somatosensory cortex and in a somatotopically organized manner.

Previous work by Chen, Friedman, and Roe [10] found that the funneling illusion could also be extended to an object one is holding. Chen *et al.* [10] found that if tactile stimuli are delivered simultaneously to two fingers, an illusory "out-of-the-body" sense of touch is experienced in the intervening space between the fingers on the object they are holding. This elicited activation in a single focal point between the representation of each finger in the primary somatosensory cortex of squirrel monkeys. The amplitude of the activation in the merged focal site between each finger's cortical representation for each finger was comparable to the amplitude of the activation when each finger was stimulated individually with the same intensity [10]. Overall, these findings suggest that we can experience a sense of touch on objects that are not in direct contact with our bodies.

Scholars make use of the tactile funneling illusion to elicit robust tactile experiences using fewer points of contact for vibrotactile actuators [22, 39, 40]. However, this line of work has primarily focused on tactile experiences in the absence of information from other senses [9, 10, 15, 22, 36, 39], and little is known about the influence of other sensory cues on this tactile illusion [29, 30, 38]. This poses a problem for potential real-world applications as well as our understanding of our sense of touch more generally, because, we live in a multisensory environment wherein the brain integrates all available information from our different senses in order to create a coherent perception of the world around us [47]. Thus, to develop a comprehensive understanding of tactile illusions like the tactile funneling illusion, and orient developers toward fruitful applications, it is necessary to examine these illusions in a multisensory context. Given the dominant role of vision in our everyday lives, it is important to know whether these tactile illusions can occur in contexts in which users have their eyes open, and if so, how visual information interacts with these illusory tactile percepts.

Lee *et al.* [29] suggests that it is possible to experience the "out-of-the-body" tactile funneling illusion when participants have their eyes open and are receiving vibrotactile stimuli delivered to their index fingers. The results of this study suggest that the tactile funneling illusion can be experienced when the eyes are open, and when visual information (e.g., a virtual ruler rendered between the fingers) is available to help understand where the tactile stimuli are coming from. However, one limitation of this study is that the visual information was displayed on a 2D screen in front of the participants, rather than from the natural first-person perspective. It is possible

that these findings merely reflect a shift in attention away from the participants' actual hands, rather than a genuine tactile experience. For this reason, it is not clear whether the "out-of-the-body" illusory sense of touch can be experienced from a first-person perspective, and if so, how visual information interacts with haptic information.

2.2 Avatar Embodiment

Avatar embodiment, or the sense of self that is associated with a virtual or robotic body, is an important area of research in the field of VR, telepresence, and human-computer interaction. The way we perceive object sizes and distances in the real world can be influenced by our physical bodies [18, 44–46]. Research in this area suggests that multisensory signals are combined by the brain to tell us this body is mine [17, 27, 32, 33]. By manipulating one of the sensory signals (i.e., visual, tactile, proprioceptive, and sensorimotor), the brain can be tricked, thus generating an experience of ownership over a virtual body [19].

Avatar embodiment can change haptic perception, as González-Franco and Berger [17] revealed in their study. They conducted a series of experiments to study the effect of visuo-haptic feedback on the illusion of touch in VR. During the experiments, participants received vibrotactile feedback from two independent controllers and were presented with visual stimuli, to induce an illusory sense of touch on a virtual object in VR. Participants were either embodied in an avatar or not. After each trial, participants were asked to report where they perceived the illusory tactile sensations. Interestingly, the illusion of touch on the virtual object was significantly stronger for those who had an avatar body than those who did not. These results suggest that having a virtual body might be critical for producing accurate spatialisation of touch from more ambiguous haptic feedback within the VE. Moreover, the embodiment in different types of avatars or virtual body alternations (e.g., changes in size, gender, or race) may significantly affect haptic perception [4, 37, 45].

2.3 Intersensory Integration

The haptic illusion literature proposes that users' haptic experiences are influenced not just by tactile signals, but also by visual and auditory stimulation [24]. This is significant because VR technologies frequently provide realistic visual and auditory stimulation, but not haptic stimulation. A recent study explored whether visual and auditory cues can enhance tactile sensations, including perceptions of the physical characteristics (i.e., roughness and stiffness) of virtual mobile gadgets in a mixed-reality setting. The results showed that visual and auditory cues can influence haptic experiences of virtual objects in VR, with auditory cues potentially being more broadly applicable than visual cues. Particularly, participants' tactile perception of virtual gadgets in motion was influenced by both visual and auditory cues when the gadget's motion was generated by them (i.e., active touch), but only by auditory cues when the gadget was observed moving (i.e., passive touch).

2.4 Uncanny Valley

The uncanny valley is a phenomenon in which a robot or virtual being that is almost, but not quite, human-like in its appearance or behaviour causes a sense of unease or revulsion in the viewer.

In relation to avatar embodiment, the uncanny valley can play a role in how a user perceives and interacts with their virtual body. If the avatar is not realistic enough or is too different from the user's own body, it can create a sense of disconnect and unease, making it difficult for the user to feel fully embodied and in control of the avatar. Additionally, if the avatar's movements or facial expressions are not accurate or natural enough, it can also cause a sense of discomfort and reduce the sense of presence and body ownership [11]. Researchers in the field of avatar embodiment and VR are aware of the uncanny valley and try to avoid it by creating more realistic avatars, with an accurate representation of the user's

movements and facial expressions. They also try to provide more sensory feedback and more sophisticated control interfaces in order to create a more realistic and believable embodiment.

The uncanny valley can also apply to haptic feedback. Haptic feedback is important for creating a sense of embodiment and body ownership, as it allows the user to feel like they are interacting with a real physical object. However, if the haptic feedback is not realistic or accurate enough, it can create a sense of disconnect and discomfort, known as the "uncanny valley of haptics" [6]. This can occur if the haptic feedback does not match the user's expectations or if it is not in sync with the visual and auditory feedback. For example, if the haptic feedback is not strong enough or if it is delayed, it can create a sense of disconnect between the user and the virtual object, making it difficult for the user to feel fully embodied and in control of the avatar. Additionally, if the haptic feedback is not realistic enough, it can create a sense of discomfort and reduce the sense of presence and body ownership.

To avoid the uncanny valley of haptics, researchers in the field of avatar embodiment and VR are developing more advanced haptic devices that can provide a wider range of sensations, such as temperature and pressure, and are trying to improve the synchrony between the haptic, visual and auditory feedback. They also try to provide more sensory feedback and more sophisticated control interfaces in order to create a more realistic and believable embodiment.

3 OBJECTIVES

This paper presents the implementation results of the "funneling illusion" in immersive VR with the aim of exploring the relationship between perception, presence, and body ownership, focusing on the holistic nature of multimodal perception. It extends the scope of previous work by Berger *et al.* [5] by introducing conditions with auditory feedback that correspond to those of haptic feedback to explore the relationship between the interaction of auditory and haptic feedback with different aspects of presence and body ownership.

Our primary goals are to present a prototype VR system that will help us in the future to determine whether there is an improvement in presence with sophisticated multimodal cues as opposed to bimodal cues. Multimodal cues can be presented via visual, auditory and haptic sensory information. Although the system has not been evaluated yet, our hypotheses for this research were formulated and are summarised below. Overall, audio-haptic feedback is expected to make a greater contribution to presence compared to visuo-haptic feedback.

- H1. The provision of multimodal cues (visual, auditory, and haptic) in VR environments will lead to an improvement in presence compared to bimodal cues (visual and haptic) alone.
- H2. Spatialized auditory feedback will enhance the illusory sense of touch in VR, leading to a greater sense of presence and body ownership.
- H3. Providing users with a sense of control over their avatar will increase the sense of agency and lead to more successful induction of the body ownership illusion in VR.

The first hypothesis favours the multisensory context of VR environments. The second hypothesis favours the provision of spatialised auditory feedback in illusory experiments. The third hypothesis highlights the importance of providing the user with a sense of control over the avatar, which greatly enhances the sense of agency. This is an important ingredient for successful body ownership illusion induction.

4 THEORETICAL CONTRIBUTIONS

The tactile funneling illusion has the potential to contribute to the field of VR by providing a new way to enhance the sense of touch

in VR experiments. As previously mentioned, the illusion can be used by applying touch to one body part but making the participant perceive it as coming from another, which can make the experience more realistic and immersive. The funneling illusion can help researchers improve their understanding of the brain’s interpretation and processing of touch in VR. This can lead to the development of more realistic haptic feedback in VR and a better mapping between the virtual and real world. Also, this can help to improve the sense of presence and body ownership for the users, which are key factors in making VR experiences more immersive.

Additionally, using the funneling illusion in VR experiments can also provide insights into how the brain processes and interprets touch information in general. This can have implications for fields beyond VR, such as prosthetics and robotics, where haptic feedback plays a critical role. The use of the funneling illusion in VR experiments is a recent development and further research is necessary to grasp its full benefits. However, prior study outcomes show promise and it could serve as a helpful tool for VR and haptic researchers.

5 IMPLEMENTATION

For the purposes of the experiment, a prototype VR simulation environment was created using the Unity Game Engine [23] (version 2020.3.26f1). The Valve Index headset and controllers were used which uses a combination of 87 sensors including capacitive sensors for proximity sensing and tracking of no-contact end-points e.g. fingers, and a pressure sensitive grip to sense grabbing, and features a Linear Resonant Actuator (LRA) for vibration haptic feedback which we will use to simulate tactile sensations in the VE. The simulation takes place in a laboratory environment (i.e., office room) and the VR environment was built to resemble this exact room. The VR environment is depicted in Fig. 2. The user is expected to stay seated in front of a desk throughout the experiment and hold a controller in both hands; this enables tracking of the hands’ location in real-time (Fig. 3). We note here that all 3D objects, including characters in the scene were designed at scale; one unit in the VR space corresponds to one centimeter in the real world.

Figure 2: VR prototype environment implemented in the Unity3D Game Engine. The virtual environment resembles the physical room.

In the future, we wish to investigate how visual, auditory and tactile stimuli affect the participant’s perception of reality. It is thus important to establish both a strong sense of agency (the participant recognises an action as a result of their own volition) and ownership (the perception that the artificial body belongs to the participant) [14, 48].

To enhance the sense of agency, we need to ensure that the avatar’s arm and hand motion is smooth and synchronised despite the limited amount of data available to us from the VR controllers. To determine the positions and orientation of the avatar’s arm, hand and joint, and to achieve smooth realistic hand gestures, we use the Forwards And Backwards Reaching Inverse Kinematics (FABRIK) implementation of Aristidou and Lasenby [3], which is publicly available as part of the Unity3D Toolkit and is a highly optimised solution. The method achieves the desired motion by performing several iterations of a

Figure 3: The posture of a participant during a pilot study, while holding the virtual ruler.

forwards and backwards step, each time repositioning the joints comprising the arm and hand, in a constrained manner as to not violate the initial conditions posed or any natural laws. The resulting motion appears smooth and does not exhibit any discontinuities. Due to the constrained pose of the human participants (Fig. 3), there are not ambiguous solutions generated by the Inverse Kinematic solver.

To further promote the sense of ownership over the virtual body, a virtual mirror was positioned at head level facing the avatar so that the participant has sight of their virtual body and movements in real-time. This is a standard procedure in designing experiments involving embodiment, as proposed in the work of Spanlang *et al.* [46] where it is evident that the mirror improved the sense of ownership and González-Franco *et al.* [21] where there is experimental evidence suggesting enhanced sense of agency.

Once the user puts on the VR headset, they are prompted to select the gender of their virtual avatar. Two ready-to-use characters from the Character Creator 3 Demo Project Pack were used, and these are depicted in Fig. 4. After selecting the gender, the participant is placed in front of a virtual desk in a replicated virtual room, with a virtual mirror facing their avatar.

The following scenario is implemented. A ruler, with 15 equally spaced markings, is placed in front of the participant (Fig. 5). A red ball is dropped from a height of 10 centimeters on the annotated ruler surface at one of the following 5 distinct points between the two end points of the ruler: markings 0, 4, 8, 12 and 15. Note that the end points of the ruler were clearly marked with capital letters ‘L’ and ‘R’ as shown in Fig. 5. When the ball hits the ruler a characteristic sound indicating a ball hitting a hard surface is heard in the headset’s earphones and the VR controllers vibrate.

The intensity of both the characteristic sound and vibration from

(a) male character

(b) female character

Figure 4: The two characters from the Character Creator 3 Demo Project Pack used in the VR simulation.

either earphone and controller (left or right) is inversely proportional to the distance of the ball from the two endpoints of the ruler, that is, if the ball is to bounce at distance x units from the 'L' marker, the intensity of the sound and vibration will be proportional to x^{-1} for the left earphone and controller and proportional to $(15-x)^{-1}$ for the right earphone and controller. The ball hits the ruler a total of 10 times, that is, each of the 5 distinct points on the ruler is hit in total twice, but these occurrences do not necessarily happen consecutively or in any particular order. Each time a hit occurs, the ball bounces off the ruler 3 times for a total of 3 seconds, and each bounce is accompanied by the characteristic sound and controller vibration. In between distinct hits, 221 milliseconds elapse.

Figure 5: The annotated ruler is placed on the surface of the desk.

Three conditions are implemented which will be used for a formal user study in the near future:

- Condition 1: visual, tactile, and auditory stimuli are used,
- Condition 2: no visual stimuli used,
- Condition 3: no tactile stimuli used,

where visual stimuli mean the appearance or not of a red bouncing ball, tactile stimuli mean the vibrations induced by the VR controllers, and auditory stimuli mean the characteristic sound heard from the VR headset earphones.

Each of the 3 conditions is implemented in two settings. In the first setting, the annotated ruler is positioned on the desk within reach of the avatar's hand, whereas in the second one, the ruler is positioned at a height of 20 cm above the desk's surface, to test how the height of the ruler affects perception. Figure 7 shows a still taken during the experiment. The red ball is shown hitting the ruler as in testing conditions 1 and 3 and the ruler is placed on the desk's surface, within reach of the avatar's hands as in the first testing setting.

For each trial, the vibrators in the handheld controllers were set to one of five different amplitudes (0, .25, .5, .75, or 1.0), as originally proposed by Alles [2]. The activation of the vibrators was brief and lasted for 221 milliseconds, which was initiated 3 seconds after the start of the experiment or the previous trial. The linear modulation of the pulses was achieved by delivering simultaneous vibrotactile pulses of different amplitudes to the left and right controllers.

The amplitudes combinations delivered to the left and right controllers were 1, 0; 0.75, 0.25; 0.5, 0.5; 0.25, 0.75; 0, 1, respectively. These combinations corresponded to pulse amplitude modulations P1-P5, each of which was intended to elicit the illusion that the vibrations were spatially located in one of five different locations (Fig. 6). One of the five pulse amplitude modulations was delivered per trial, with each delivered in random order and repeated 10 times throughout the experiment. In a future experiment, this will allow us to collect data on the users' perception of the spatial location of the vibrations delivered to their hands.

6 DISCUSSION

The "tactile funneling illusion" refers to the phenomenon where a person perceives a touch on a specific body part even when the actual touch is applied to a different part of the body. This illusion is often used in research on touch perception and haptics in VR, as

Figure 6: The amplitude rendering for funneling creates phantom sensations at five different points (P1 to P5). For instance, to generate a phantom sensation at P2, Left Controller's Amplitude is set at 0.75 and the Right Controller's amplitude is set at 0.25.

Figure 7: Still from the VR environment. The annotated ruler is placed within reach of the avatar's hands during the first testing setting of the experiment and the red ball is apparent as in testing conditions 1 and 3.

it can provide insights into how the brain processes and interprets touch information.

In the context of Berger *et al.*'s work [5], the authors propose using the funneling illusion in an immersive VR setup to improve the sense of touch. The idea is that by applying touch to one body part but making the participant perceive it as coming from another, the experience can be made more realistic and immersive. Here, we plan to test this idea by building a prototype VR system and conducting experiments to see how well the illusion works in VR, within a multisensory environment. It is worth noting that the funneling illusion is a relatively new concept in VR research, so it is still an open question as to how well it can be used to improve the sense of touch in VR. We expect that our results will provide a better understanding of how the funneling illusion can be used to improve the user experience in VR. It is also worth noting that the funneling illusion is not the only way to improve the sense of touch in VR, there are other methods such as for example, creating realistic haptic feedback and providing a good mapping between the virtual and real world. The funneling illusion can be a great addition to these methods as it could add a new layer of realism to the sense of touch in VR.

Berger *et al.* [5] sought to examine whether an illusory sense of touch could be elicited in an immersive VR setting using the tactile funneling illusion. The results of their Experiment 3 show that an illusory sense of touch can be experienced in the intervening space between the hands in an eye-open setting in VR when simultaneous vibrotactile feedback is delivered to the left and right hand via handheld controllers. However, their study was limited by a small sample size of only ten participants. Lee *et al.* [29] also used a limited sample size of only fourteen participants. A sample size this

small weakens the study's power and widens the margin of error, making the results unreliable. In a future experiment, we aim to recruit healthy participants to address these issues.

One of the interesting findings from González-Franco and Berger's study [17], was that the participants' objective and subjective reports of the illusion of touch (i.e., the perceived location of touch) differed between the avatar body and no-body conditions. When measuring subtle changes in other aspects of the experience, like presence and body ownership, there may be disconnects in subjective reporting. Moreover, the effects of the BOI might be compromised by the fact that the participants have the option to choose between a male and a female avatar. The lack of the option to select physical characteristics, such as skin colour or body size, would have made the avatars more personalised. However, creating self-avatars would have been costly and time-consuming, and would have required a smaller sample size. Drifts in haptic perception may also be observed when participants are embodied in avatars that do not match their size, gender or race.

Another limitation is the error owed to Inverse Kinematics position estimation which is in general of the same order as the distances between intermediate markings on the ruler (of the order of 1 centimeter). This may affect the participant's perception of distance, especially when testing the second condition of the experiment where the participant has no visual depiction of the ball's location and their perception of space may be influenced by other visual stimuli e.g. position of hands relative to the ruler. As a result, it will be difficult to report the perceived location of the phantom sensations accurately. We propose that future studies measuring haptic perception for the tactile funneling illusion, use a more accurate Inverse Kinematics method.

One challenge in delivering spatial audio in VR is making sure the audio changes with the movements of the virtual objects. Spatial audio utilizes 360-degree environments to simulate reality. For the first two conditions, the 3D sound will be delivered through the earphones of the VR headset, while the user is sitting stationary. In the third condition, spatial audio will be delivered with a visual cue (e.g., a virtual ball). For these three parts, the user will be asked to find the source location while remaining in the same spot. All the users are expected to be able to find the objects accurately in the third condition. It might have been more appropriate to use noise-cancelling headphones, instead of earphones, to block out background noise and avoid distractions.

One of the main issues with avatar embodiment is latency, which is the delay between a user's movements and the corresponding movements of the avatar. High latency can create a disconnect between the user and the avatar, making it difficult for the user to feel like they are in control of the avatar and reducing the sense of presence and body ownership. Another issue with avatar embodiment is agency, or the sense of control and influence over the avatar. If the avatar does not respond accurately or quickly enough to the user's movements, it can create a sense of disconnect between the user and the avatar, reducing the sense of embodiment.

Additionally, if the avatar is not able to accurately represent the user's movements, it can create a sense of dissociation between the user's sense of self and the avatar, reducing the sense of body ownership. Latency is considered one of the biggest issues in body ownership research. It is crucial to reduce latency as much as possible to create a realistic and believable embodiment. This can be achieved by using high-speed networks, reducing the number of data packets that need to be sent and received, and using advanced compression techniques. Additionally, researchers are also trying to improve the sense of agency by using more advanced and realistic avatars, providing more sensory feedback, and using more sophisticated control interfaces. To create a convincing sense of embodiment and body ownership, it is important to address both latency and agency issues.

It is possible that using commercial tactile gloves as a replacement for VR handles could affect participants' sense of presence and body ownership in VR. The mismatch between the participants' physical hand gestures and the avatar's hand gestures could break the illusion of embodiment and reduce the sense of ownership over the virtual body. Additionally, if tactile feedback provided by the gloves is not well-calibrated or does not match the VE, it could also negatively impact the sense of presence. However, it ultimately depends on the specific design and implementation of the tactile gloves and how well they can mimic the VR handles.

There are many variables that can affect the effectiveness of using tactile gloves as a replacement for VR handles, such as the intensity and type of auditory and vibrotactile feedback provided. It is important to conduct pre-experiments to determine the appropriate level of feedback for the specific VE and task at hand. To enhance the user experience in VR, it's crucial to calibrate the feedback provided by the gloves accurately to match the VE. This can increase the sense of presence and body ownership for the participants. Moreover, the design of the gloves, including their ability to imitate VR controllers, is also important to consider. Nevertheless, it's important to note that tactile feedback alone may not suffice to create a sense of presence and body ownership in VR, as visual and auditory cues may also play a crucial role.

7 CONCLUSION

This paper provides the implementation of the funneling illusion in VR in order to understand the sense of touch. We provide methods for enhancing the human sense of touch or the information that is delivered tactilely from multimodal devices, wearable devices, and VR settings where the user has few physical points of contact. According to previous findings, having a virtual avatar could play a significant role in accurately specializing touch within the VR from more ambiguous haptic feedback. In the future, we plan to evaluate formally the prototype with 30 participants.

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